

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14895057

Influence Of Social Interaction On Academic Performance Of Secondary School Students In Rivers-West Senatorial District Of Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of social interaction on academic performance of Senior Secondary Two (S.S.2) students in selected public schools in the Rivers-West Senatorial District. The study employed descriptive survey design. Three research questions guided the study and three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study is 2,650 Senior Secondary Two (S.S.2) students in selected public schools in the Rivers-West Senatorial District. The sample size was 212 students which was selected through simple random technique. The instrument for data collection was “Social Interaction and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SIAPQ). Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions while Chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that; Student-teacher interaction, student-student interaction and student-parent interaction have significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District. The study recommended among others that; Educators should Promote Collaborative Learning for Student-Student Interaction. Introduce group projects, peer-review assignments, and collaborative problem-solving tasks. There should be Open Communication Channels for Student-Teacher Interaction. Establish regular one-on-one check-ins, incorporate feedback sessions, and create a supportive classroom environment where questions and discussions are encouraged.

Keywords: Social interaction, Student-student interaction, Student-teacher interaction, Student-parents interaction and Academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a noticeable decline in academic performance among students across various educational levels. This trend is particularly evident in subjects such as mathematics, science, and literacy, where test scores have shown a decline globally. According to research by Reardon (2019), socio-economic disparities could play an important role in this decline, as students from disadvantaged backgrounds are more likely to attend underfunded schools and have limited access to educational resources. These inequities exacerbate the academic performance gap, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria and specifically low-income communities, where students face additional challenges such as food insecurity and lack of parental support. Academic performance is the measurable outcomes of a student's learning progress, typically assessed through grades, standardized test scores, and other indicators of intellectual proficiency.

It encompasses not only the acquisition of knowledge but also the application of skills and critical thinking in educational settings. According to York, Gibson, and Rankin (2015), academic performance is a multidimensional construct that reflects a student's ability to meet institutional standards and expectations across different subjects and disciplines. It is often used to evaluate both individual student success and the effectiveness of educational programs and policies. In addition to external factors such as socioeconomic disparities and the pandemic, rising mental health issues and interpersonal relationship among students may have contributed to falling academic performance rates. The increasing prevalence of anxiety, depression, and stress among students can negatively impact their ability to focus, engage in learning activities, and complete assignments on time. According to Lee (2021), mental health and social factors may also be linked to lower academic outcomes, as students experiencing emotional distress often struggle to meet academic demands. Students' performance is evidence in their level of regular attendance to school, their level class participation or involvement in class discussion and assignment completion among others.

Class participation, school attendance, and assignment completion may be key factors influencing academic performance and overall student success. Educational research consistently highlights the importance of these variables in creating a conducive learning environment that fosters both cognitive and behavioural development. Each of these elements has a unique and complementary role in shaping students' academic outcomes. As schools increasingly focus on holistic education, understanding the interplay of these factors becomes essential for improving student engagement and achievement. Class participation refers to the active engagement of students in classroom activities, discussions, and interactions. Studies have shown that students who actively participate in class are more likely to retain information, think critically, and develop a deeper understanding of course material. According to Rocca (2010), class participation not only enhances comprehension but also builds students' communication skills and confidence.

Participation fosters a collaborative learning atmosphere where students learn from both peers and instructors, promoting the exchange of diverse perspectives. Thus, encouraging class participation is crucial for optimizing student learning outcomes. Research by Johnson and Johnson, (2019) stated that students in the cooperative learning groups performed significantly better academically, showed increased motivation, and demonstrated better information retention than those in the control group. Students who engaged in peer learning reported feeling more confident and valued the support received from classmates.

In addition, attendance may also play a critical role in determining students' academic success. Consistent attendance allows students to fully engage with course material, build upon previous lessons, and actively participate in learning activities. According to Gottfried (2010), chronic absenteeism negatively impacts student performance, leading to learning gaps, poor grades, and decreased graduation rates. Moreover, regular attendance helps develop students' time management and responsibility, preparing them for future endeavours. Schools with low absenteeism rates tend to have better academic achievement overall, further emphasizing the importance of regular school attendance.

Social interaction on other hand is the process by which individuals act and react in relation to others, encompassing a broad range of interpersonal exchanges, including communication, cooperation, conflict, and collaboration. In an educational setting, social interaction is critical as it allows students to share ideas, learn from peers, and receive guidance from authority figures such as teachers and parents. Vygotsky (1978) emphasized the role of social interaction in cognitive development, arguing that learning is a fundamentally social process where students construct knowledge through interaction with others. Student-teacher interaction involves the communication and relational dynamics between educators and their students. Research consistently shows that positive student-teacher relationships are crucial for fostering academic engagement and performance. Pianta, Stuhlman & Hamre, (2015) found that students who experience supportive and responsive teacher relationships tend to exhibit higher motivation, better academic achievement, and greater emotional well-being. Effective student-teacher interactions can create a supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable asking questions, participating in

discussions, and seeking help when needed. Conversely, negative or distant interactions can lead to disengagement, lower academic performance, and a lack of interest in school.

Another aspect is the student-student interaction which refers to the peer relationships and collaborations that occur within an educational setting. This type of interaction plays a critical role in the development of communication, teamwork, and social skills, all of which are essential for academic success. Peer interactions, especially in group work and classroom discussions, allow students to exchange ideas, offer diverse perspectives, and support each other's learning processes. According to Johnson and Johnson (2019), cooperative learning environments where students engage in group activities and collaborative problem-solving have been linked to improved academic outcomes, as they encourage active participation and deeper understanding of content. Also the interaction between students and their parents is another influential factor in academic performance. Parental involvement in a child's education, such as helping with homework, attending school events, and maintaining open communication, has been shown to positively impact academic achievement. According to Hill and Tyson (2019), students whose parents are actively involved in their education tend to have better grades, higher test scores, and more positive attitudes toward school. This interaction also fosters a sense of accountability and motivation in students, as they recognize that their parents are invested in their academic success. On the other hand, lack of parental involvement can result in reduced support and lower academic performance.

Statement Of The Problem

Academic performance is influenced by various factors, one of which could also include social interaction within educational environments. Social interaction, which involves the communication and relationships between students, teachers, and parents, seems to play a crucial role in shaping students' learning experiences. However, the research has observed a vacuum of social interaction among students these key stakeholders with secondary schools in Rivers-West Senatorial District. Students rather seek attention on social media and other platforms since the needed interactions between teachers and parents may be lacking. This poses a treat for them to fully adjust academically. It is also evidence that this lack of effective social interaction can hinder academic success, leading to disengagement, poor motivation, and reduced cognitive development. It has also been observed that one of the most detrimental factors to academic performance is the absence of strong student-teacher interactions. When students do not engage with their teachers, either due to fear, disinterest, or a lack of accessibility, they may miss out on critical feedback and guidance necessary for their academic development. Also, student-student interaction, particularly through collaborative, or group learning and peer discussions, could play a key role in reinforcing classroom learning. If students lack opportunities to engage with their peers, they may also miss out on the benefits of collaborative problem-solving, knowledge sharing, and social learning. Parental involvement, such as helping with homework or attending school events, positively could also influence students' academic engagement. However, in cases where parents are disengaged, either due to work pressures, lack of awareness, or socioeconomic constraints, students are less likely to feel supported in their academic endeavours. It is against this background that this study sought to investigate the influence of social interaction on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does student-teacher interaction influence Senior Secondary Two (S.S.2) students in selected public schools in the Rivers-West Senatorial District?
2. How does student-student interaction influence academic performance of secondary school students?
3. What is the influence of student parents' interaction on academic performance of secondary school students?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Student-teacher interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of senior secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.
2. Student-student interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary school students
3. Students-parents interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary school students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted a descriptive research design. The population of the study was 2,650 Senior Secondary Two (S.S.2) students in selected public schools in the Rivers-West Senatorial District. The sample size of 212 was randomly selected. The instrument for data collection was a 15 item self-constructed questionnaire titled Social Interaction and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SIAPQ). The questionnaire was divided into 3 clusters based on the variables of the study. Cluster A contained items 1-5 which elicited information on student-student interaction and academic performance. Cluster B contained items 6 – 10 which sought information on student-teacher interaction and academic performance. Cluster C contained items 11-15 which elicited information on students-parents interaction and academic performance. The desired responses were tabulated on a four-point rating scale with a response mode of Strongly Agree (SA)-4 Agree (A)-3 Disagree (D)-2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)-1 Data collected from the respondents (students) was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The cut-off point of 2.50 was used to determine positive impact while anything less than 2.50 was regarded as negative impact. Chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does student-teacher interaction influence students' academic performance in Rivers-West Senatorial District?*

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for Influence of student-teacher interaction on academic performance of Students in Rivers-West Senatorial District

SN	Item	SA	A	D	SD	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	I don't usually have problems doing my assignments because my teachers are willing to explain difficult topics even after the lessons.	56	75	36	45	212	2.67	1.086	Agreed
2	I sometimes meet with my teachers after lesson to get more explanations on a difficult topic.	67	45	65	35	212	2.68	1.089	Agreed
3	I usually learn new ideas from relating with my teachers.	60	82	28	42	212	2.75	1.074	Agreed
4	I have learnt better writing skills from by interacting with my teachers.	71	75	66	0	212	2.71	1.227	Agreed
5	My interaction with my teachers has also helped to develop my vocabulary.	67	59	47	39	212	2.73	1.097	Agreed
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation							2.71	1.11	Agreed

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 1 finding indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 with corresponding standard deviations as. 2.67 (1.086), 2.68 (1.089), 2.75 (1.074) 2.71 (1.227), 2.73 (1.097), Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point as indicated on the cluster mean of 2.71 and standard deviation of 1.11. This implies that student-teacher interaction have significant influence on academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Research Question

How does student-student interaction influence academic performance of secondary school students?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for Influence of student-students interaction on academic performance of Students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

SN	Item	SA	A	D	SD	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	I usually learn new words from reading with my mates.	65	70	61	16	212	2.87	.940	Agreed
7	I often carry out my assignment with the help of my class mates	70	38	45	59	212	2.56	1.212	Agreed
8	It is easier to student in group with my class mates than studying alone.	56	74	43	39	212	2.69	1.055	Agreed
9	I understand some lessons better with I rehears with my mates.	68	74	34	36	212	2.82	1.065	Agreed
10	I often score high in exams with I study with my class mates.	58	60	51	43	212	2.63	1.092	Agreed
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation							2.71	1.07	Agreed

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 2 finding indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 with corresponding standard deviations as. 2.87 (.940), 2.56 (1.212), 2.69 (1.055) 2.82 (1.065), 2.63 (1.092), Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point as indicated on the cluster mean of 2.71 and standard deviation of 1.07. This implies that student-student interaction have significant influence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Research Question

What is the influence of student parents' interaction on academic performance of senior secondary school students?

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for Influence of student-parent interaction on academic performance of Students in Rivers-West Senatorial District

SN	Item	SA	A	D	SD	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	I usually seek assistance from my parents when I have a difficult assignment.	74	75	40	23	212	2.94	.986	Agreed
12	My father/mother usually assist me to develop my time table and follow it accordingly.	71	59	55	27	212	2.82	1.038	Agreed
13	Discussing my lessons with my parents usually help me to understand better.	67	76	37	32	212	2.84	1.036	Agreed
14	My parents sometimes guide me on how to attempt questions in a test or examination.	23	112	50	27	212	2.62	.843	Agreed
15	Reading with my father/mother also help me to learn new words.	80	39	55	38	212	2.76	1.141	Agreed
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation							2.80	1.06	Agreed

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 3 finding indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 with corresponding standard deviations as. 2.94 (.986), 2.82 (1.038), 2.84 (1.036) 2.62 (.843), 2.76 (1.141), Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point as indicated on the cluster mean of 2.80 and standard deviation of 1.06. This implies that student-student interaction have significant influence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X²) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Student-teacher interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Table 4: Chi-Square Test for the Influence of Student-teacher interaction on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District

Reponses Mode	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Df	Level Sign	X ²	P.value	Decision
SA	321	53.0	3	0.05	247.358	0.000	Significant
A	336	53.0					
D	176	53.0					
SD	227	53.0					

Source: Field Work 2024

Hypothesis 1 result shows X² 247.358, df= 3, and P-value= 0.000. Since P-value 0.00<0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that Student-teacher interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District is rejected. This implies that Student-teacher interaction has significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 2

Student-student interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Table 5: Chi-Square Test for the Influence of Student-student interaction on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District

Reponses Mode	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Df	Level Sign	X ²	P.value	Decision
SA	317	53.0	3	0.05	242.491	0.000	Significant
A	316	53.0					
D	234	53.0					
SD	193	53.0					

Source: Field Work 2024

Hypothesis 2 result shows X² 242.491, df= 3, and P-value= 0.000. Since P-value 0.00<0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that Student-student interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District is rejected. This implies that Student-student interaction have significant influence on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 3 Student-parent interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary school students.

Table 6: *Chi-Square Test for the Influence of Student-parent interaction on academic performance of secondary students in Makurdi Local Government Area*

Reponses Mode	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Df	Level Sign	X ²	P.value	Decision
SA	315	53.0	3	0.05	176.302	0.000	Significant
A	361	53.0					
D	237	53.0					
SD	147	53.0					

Source: Field Work 2024

Hypothesis 3 result shows X² 176.302, df= 3, and P-value= 0.000. Since P-value 0.00<0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that Student-parent interaction has no significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District is rejected. This implies that Student-parents interaction has significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this study was based on the result hypotheses. The three null hypotheses that were formulated and tested have been all rejected.

The first finding of the study revealed that Student-teacher interaction have significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District. Mean scores from students responds indicated that; they don't usually have problems doing their assignments because their teachers are willing to explain difficult topics even after the lessons. Students also agreed that they sometimes meet with their teachers after lesson to get more explanations on a difficult topic. Students usually learn new ideas from relating with their teachers. They have learnt better writing skills from by interacting with their teachers. It also revealed that students' interaction with their teachers has also helped to develop their vocabulary. The finding is in line with Pianta, Belsky, Vandergrift, Houts & Morrison (2018) who found that students who experienced higher levels of emotionally supportive and instructional interactions with teachers showed significant improvements in literacy and math scores over the study period. Emotional support from teachers correlated with increased motivation, while instructional support directly influenced comprehension and skills in the assessed subjects. It also agrees with the findings of Allen, Gregory, Mikami, Lun, Hamre & Pianta (2013) that, students with teachers who received training on relationship-building techniques demonstrated improved engagement, better attendance, and higher grades than those in the control group. Supportive teacher interactions were associated with an increase in students' intrinsic motivation and academic effort.

The second hypothesis revealed that Student-student interaction have significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District. Students' responses shows that; they usually learn new words from reading with their mates. Students often carry out their assignment with the help of their class mates. Students agreed that it is easier to learn in a group with their class mates than studying alone. Students understand some lessons better when they rehears with their mates. A good number of students agreed that they often score high in exams when they study with their class mates. This finding agrees with Johnson & Johnson, (2019) whose study found that students in the cooperative learning groups performed significantly better academically, showed increased motivation, and demonstrated better information retention than those in the control group. Students who engaged in peer learning reported feeling more confident and valued the support received from classmates. It is also in line with the findings of Gillie, (2016) that, students who engaged in peer-led discussions performed significantly better in post-tests, especially in critical thinking and problem-solving tasks. The results

suggested that peer interactions encouraged students to engage deeply with the material, ask questions, and collaboratively explore solutions. Students also reported higher levels of academic confidence and engagement.

The third hypothesis revealed that Student-parents interaction have significant influence on academic performance of secondary students in Rivers-West Senatorial District. Mean scores from students responses revealed that; they usually seek assistance from their parents when they have a difficult assignment. Students also agreed that their parents usually assist them to develop a time table and follow it accordingly. Discussing their lessons with their parents usually also help them to understand better. Students' parents sometimes guide them on how to attempt questions in a test or examination. It also revealed that reading with their parents also help them to learn new words. This finding correlates with the findings of Hill & Tyson (2019) that, parental academic socialization discussing educational goals, expectations, and the value of education had the most significant positive impact on students' academic performance. Home-based involvement, such as helping with homework, also showed positive effects, though to a lesser degree. It also agrees with Fan and Chen (2015) whose study found that parental involvement that fostered students' autonomy and academic self-concept was especially effective. Fan and Chen recommended that parents prioritize setting high expectations and engaging in regular academic discussions with their children.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that social interaction have significant influence on students' academic performance in Rivers-West Senatorial District. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Educators should Promote Collaborative Learning for Student-Student Interaction. Introduce group projects, peer-review assignments, and collaborative problem-solving tasks.
2. There should be Open Communication Channels for Student-Teacher Interaction. Establish regular one-on-one check-ins, incorporate feedback sessions, and create a supportive classroom environment where questions and discussions are encouraged.
3. Parents should create a welcoming environment which will encourage children to discuss their academic needs. The school administration parents to engage in school events, monitor their child's progress, and maintain open communication about academic and personal challenges.

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